

The Threat to Democracy Posed by Extreme Wealth Inequality

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One of the greatest threats to democracy is extreme wealth inequality. When wealth becomes concentrated, it transforms into economic power, which can then be converted into political influence. This cycle, evident in countries like Russia and the United States, fuels economic polarization and undermines the very foundations of democracy.

This concern aligns with the political theory of American philosopher John Rawls, whose ideas have deeply shaped modern liberal democratic thought. Rawls' "difference principle" argues that inequalities in society are only justified if they benefit the least advantaged.

Traditionally, the idea of egalitarian capitalism has emphasized controlling income inequality in the interest of the collective good and public utility. However, until recently, the conversation largely ignored the central issue of capital itself—the ownership and concentration of wealth.

Understanding the causes of accumulated and concentrated wealth, as well as how this wealth distorts democratic institutions, is complex. A major factor is the role of the state and legal-accounting professions in facilitating multinational corporate tax avoidance.

Corporate Tax Avoidance: The Social Workers for the Rich

Corporate tax avoidance strategies and aggressive tax planning allow the wealthiest multinational companies to legally reduce their taxable income and maximize profits. Over time, these accumulated profits lead to increased capital income, creating ideal conditions for wealth accumulation.

The mechanics of tax avoidance driving wealth accumulation are straightforward. If one company pays 35% tax on €1 billion in profits while another pays just 5%, the second company will accumulate wealth far more rapidly. Not only will this company build more savings, but it will also be in a position to monopolize its market. This monopolistic power stifles competition and diminishes the innovative spirit that is

supposed to drive capitalism. The tech and pharmaceutical industries are prime examples of this phenomenon.

As profits accumulate, they are paid out as capital income to shareholders, further increasing their wealth. The real fortunes in these industries are often tied to owning shares in highly profitable companies, and these shares are concentrated among the wealthiest 0.1% of the population.

Those tasked with creating the complex structures that facilitate profit shifting effectively serve this small group of wealthy individuals. These professionals—often experts in law and finance—define the rules of the game, determining what constitutes acceptable corporate tax behavior.

In the words of Dartmouth University professor Brooke Harrington, author of *Capital Without Borders*, these transnational professionals are essentially “social workers for the rich,” navigating the complex legal landscape to protect profit and wealth.

The Role of Intellectual Property in Profit Shifting

Ireland stands as a clear beneficiary of this global profit-shifting process. In 2024, the Irish government collected a record €28 billion in corporate tax revenue—almost €40 billion if we include a one-time payment from Apple. Corporate tax now represents nearly a third of Ireland’s total tax receipts. While this might seem abnormal, it signals that Ireland remains a prime location for global profit-shifting.

These corporate tax receipts are notoriously volatile, and the Irish government has wisely set aside a portion of this revenue in a rainy-day fund. However, the government has been less forthcoming about the means by which these profits arrived in Ireland, a crucial question that international observers often ask but that remains largely absent from domestic debates. The influx of profit is closely tied to changes in global tax practices, particularly in the tech and pharmaceutical sectors, and how multinational corporations have responded to global tax reforms implemented since 2015.

Two primary factors have contributed to Ireland’s rise as a “sink” location for global profits: the end of the “double Irish” tax scheme in 2015 and a series of tax reforms initiated by the OECD and the U.S. under the leadership of Donald Trump. These changes incentivized multinational corporations to restructure their subsidiaries and move intellectual property and intangible assets from zero-tax jurisdictions in the Caribbean to low-tax jurisdictions where they have a physical presence—Ireland being one such location.

Intellectual property (IP) is what drives the value and profitability of these companies, and since 2015, profits in sectors like tech and pharma have skyrocketed. With much of their IP now licensed out of Irish-based subsidiaries, Ireland's corporate tax take has boomed as well.

In the world of intangible capital, profit shifting is primarily about the location, licensing, and pricing of intellectual property. This practice, while beneficial for Ireland's economy, has created the conditions for the concentration of wealth and the expansion of monopolistic power, ultimately undermining democratic politics.

The Double-Irish Scheme Lives On

While global policymakers have acknowledged the moral and social issues surrounding tax avoidance, the practice continues. Despite reforms and efforts to curb aggressive tax planning, Ireland remains at the heart of these global tax games. For instance, in 2021, the Irish charity Christian Aid revealed that the double-Irish tax scheme, though ostensibly dismantled, had resurfaced in Malta.

After a 2019 update to the Irish-Maltese bilateral tax treaty, which sought to close loopholes allowing Irish-registered companies to avoid taxes through Maltese tax residency, multinational companies found ways to exploit new avenues. One example is Abbott Laboratories, which created Irish subsidiaries that were tax-resident in Malta. Despite employing over 350 people in Galway, Abbott's Maltese subsidiaries—registered at the office of Matheson Law Firm—have no employees and function merely as postbox companies. Using complex IP-licensing structures, Abbott shifted hundreds of millions in profits between its subsidiaries, reducing its tax bill to just 2-4%.

Though legal, this strategy is a direct result of Ireland's tax laws, which are designed to facilitate such corporate structures. The Irish government and tax authorities are aware of this, and it is likely that many other multinationals are using similar schemes.

Why It Matters: A Democratic Crisis

Why should we care about this? Because multinational companies, like those in the pharmaceutical and tech sectors, are allowed to avoid taxes, essentially escaping the fiscal accountability that democracy demands. This process takes place with the knowledge of two European Union countries—Ireland and Malta—both of which

have facilitated this tax avoidance, depriving other nations, especially developing countries, of much-needed revenue.

As Christian Aid's Conor O'Neil has pointed out, the countries that lose the most from these practices are the poorest in the world. This is a democratic problem that undermines the global financial system and perpetuates wealth inequality.

In Ireland's privileged position within the global tax system, the real winners are the super-rich—the owners of the largest multinational corporations. This is a situation that is increasingly unacceptable in a multilateral, liberal world. Despite progress made through OECD and EU initiatives, radical tax reform is still needed to ensure that the global system of corporate taxation serves democratic principles and curbs the worst excesses of capitalism.

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